

Electron exchange studies on stannic molybdate

J. P. Rawat* and Manisha Bhardwaj

Department of Chemistry, Aligarh Muslim University, Aligarh-202 002, India

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Stannic molybdate has been used as an electron ion exchanger, in which $\text{Mo}^{\text{IV}}/\text{Mo}^{\text{V}}$ couple is responsible for redox reaction. The maximum redox capacity is 0.700 meq/g. Oxidation of various species based on redox potential has been carried out and oxidation of Fe^{II} , Sn^{II} , hydrazine, ascorbic acid, thioglycolic acid and hydroquinone achieved by batch process successfully.

Electron exchangers have found many important applications. They are being extensively used for redox purposes. The advantages of electron exchangers over the conventional methods of oxidation or reduction is their insolubility in the medium of reaction, thus the interferences caused by the unreacted redox substances can be easily separated from the substances with which they have reacted. A large number of these materials are reported in the literature¹.

Stannic molybdate has been synthesized in our laboratories and has been used as an inorganic ion exchanger for the separation of metal ions². Stannic molybdate papers have been used for the chromatographic and electrochromatographic separation of metal ions³. These papers have been used for the chromatographic separation and identification of phenols⁴. The material has been used for the detection of ferrous ions⁵ because of the reducing action of ferrous and oxidizing action of stannic molybdate where the molybdate reduces to molybdenum blue. This led us to use stannic molybdate as electron exchanger.

We report herein oxidation of various species based on the redox potential of $\text{Mo}^{\text{VI}}/\text{Mo}^{\text{V}}$ couple and the redox potential of the substrate. The oxidation of Fe^{II} , Sn^{II} , ascorbic acid, thioglycolic acid, hydrazine and hydroquinone have been achieved quantitatively using stannic molybdate as an electron exchanger.

Results and Discussion

The electron exchangers may be considered as solid oxidizing and reducing agents. They contain the species forming a redox couple and after having oxidized (or reduced) a substrate, the electron exchanger can be regenerated by a suitable oxidizing or reducing agent. The only possible change in the solution, except for the redox reaction of the substrate, is the change in pH. In stannic molybdate, it is the $\text{Mo}^{\text{VI}}/\text{Mo}^{\text{V}}$ couple which is responsible for oxidation process.

The results of the redox studies (Table 1) show that when one gram of the exchanger is taken the method works for low amount of ions, and for higher amounts, larger amount of exchanger is required. The maximum redox capacity by column process is 0.700 meq/g. When solutions containing higher amount of stannous ions is passed through one gram of the exchanger only 0.700 meq is oxidized and the rest comes out unoxidized. The electron exchange phenomenon depends on the oxidation potentials of the various redox couples and only those reductants are oxidised by the exchanger for which the oxidation potential is less than that of the $\text{Mo}^{\text{VI}}/\text{Mo}^{\text{V}}$ redox system. This is further confirmed by Ce^{III} and V^{IV} which could not be oxidized because the redox potential of the $\text{Ce}^{\text{III}}/\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}$ and $\text{V}^{\text{IV}}/\text{V}^{\text{V}}$ couples are much higher than that of the $\text{Mo}^{\text{VI}}/\text{Mo}^{\text{V}}$ couple.

Table 1. Oxidation of various substrates by stannic molybdate*

Sl. no.	Amount taken meq Sn^{II}	Amount found meq Sn^{IV}	Amount taken meq Fe^{II}	Amount found meq Fe^{III}
1	0.290	0.250	0.100	0.100
2	0.400	0.380	0.150	0.125
3	0.480	0.455	0.200	0.150
4	0.610	0.600	0.250	0.240
5	0.720	0.685	0.350	0.295
	Hydrazine	Ammonia	CH_2SHCOOH	$(\text{SCH}_2\text{COOH})_2$
1	0.225	0.200	0.100	0.100
2	0.310	0.305	0.150	0.120
3	0.405	0.380	0.250	0.180
4	0.585	0.530	0.300	0.205
5	0.675	0.645	0.375	0.290
	Hydroquinone	Quinone	$\text{C}_6\text{H}_8\text{O}_6$	$\text{C}_6\text{H}_6\text{O}_6$
1.	0.300	0.060	0.160	0.132
2.	0.420	0.086	0.272	0.272
3.	0.540	0.075	0.356	0.350
4.	0.620	0.070	0.436	0.420
5.	0.720	0.085	0.568	0.558

*Amount of exchanger taken = 1 g.

The process of oxidation of stannous ion takes nearly 1.5 h to reach the equilibrium in the batch process indicating the time required for oxidation process to complete under a given set of conditions

The molybdate group in stannic molybdate is bonded at a place which is available for electron exchange with $\text{Mo}^{\text{VI}}/\text{Mo}^{\text{V}}$ couple and is responsible for oxidation of the substrate of a suitable redox potential. Stannic molybdate, when exhausted for oxidation purposes may be reoxidized (regenerated by HNO_3).

Experimental

Stannic chloride (Loba), ammonium heptamolybdate (Merck) were used. All other chemicals were of A.R. grade. Stannic molybdate gel was prepared by mixing aqueous solutions of 0.02 M stannic chloride and 0.05 M ammonium heptamolybdate in the Sn : Mo (molar) ratio of 1 : 2 and the resulting precipitate was digested at room temperature, filtered, washed with water and dried at room temperature. To convert it to the hydrogen form it was immersed in 1–2 M nitric acid for 24 h, then washed with distilled water, filtered and dried in air.

Redox studies : Oxidation of Fe^{II} , Sn^{II} , ascorbic acid, thioglycolic acid, hydrazine and hydroquinone to their respective higher oxidation states were performed by shaking the exchanger (1 g) with their solutions for 6 h. Each substrate was determined by standard methods⁶ and the total amount oxidized by the exchanger was evaluated.

The rate of oxidation was determined by taking a weighed amount of exchanger and shaking with the solution concerned. After appropriate intervals of time, the contents of the flasks were filtered and oxidized species formed were determined.

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